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Ultrahypofractionated radiotherapy of breast cancer vs. partial breast irradiation

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Postoperative radiation therapy is considered the standard treatment after breast conserving surgery. Hypofractionated and ultrahypofractionated treatment protocols demonstrated similar results to conventionally fractionated radiotherapy, with excellent cosmetic results, better quality of life and fewer side effects. Partial breast irradiation is indicated in subgroup of patients with low or intermediate risk breast cancer with main advantage in reducing the breast volume irradiated, the treatment time and the exposure to healthy tissues. In June 2023 at Oncology Institute of Vojvodina we launched NS-dojka SRB (study No NCT05914831), a single-institution prospective phase 2 trial to compare ultrahypofractionated radiotherapy regimen for whole breast irradiation (WBI) to partial breast irradiation (PBI). One hundred patients are planned for randomisation to receive either WBI or PBI of 26Gy in 5 fraction, after R0 breast conserving surgery. Inclusion criteria meet patients with ductal invasive cancer, age ≥ 50 , tumor size ≤ 3 cm, unicentric/unifocal cancer or multifocal within 2 cm of the primary neoplasm, pN0 or pN1mi with histological grade G1 or G2. Patients who underwent neoadjuvant systemic therapy, triple negative breast cancer, patients with extensive intraductal component (EIC), associated LVI and DCIS of high nuclear grade or size > 2.5 cm were excluded from the study. Patients are followed during the treatment, 3 weeks after treatment completion and then every 3 months in the first 2 years, every 6 months in the 4th and 5th year and then once per year to assess disease control, early and late adverse effects and cosmetic result. Local control, DFS, OS and distant metastases occurrence were outcome measures of the study. The first interim analysis was performed in October 2024. In

total 30 patients were analyzed – 17 in the WBI and 13 in the PBI group. Both groups were comparable without significant differences regarding patients' age, tumor size, hormonal receptor positivity and histology tumor grade. Median follow up was 5.7 months (range 1.5-14 months). Acute adverse events occurred in 10 of patients, 6 (35.3%) in the WBI and 4 (30.8%) in the PBI group, $p=0.794$. The most frequent was radiation dermatitis that was reported in 6 (20%) patients, 4 (23.5%) in the WBI group compared to 2 (15.4%) in the PBI group, ($p=0.580$). Cosmetic result during the treatment was similar in the both groups ($p=0.830$). NS-dojka SRB trial is analyzing population of patients treated with adjuvant breast cancer radiotherapy comparing two treatment regimens. First interim analyses didn't show differences in acute adverse effect or cosmetic result. Local and distal disease control was the same in the both groups. Subsequent planned analyses will allow further evaluation of efficacy and toxicity in both treatment arms.

Keywords: Breast cancer, WBI, PBI, Ultrahypofractionated radiotherapy, NS-dojka SRB

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